

Chemical Composition and Biological Activities of *Hyptis suaveolens* Essential Oil: A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract

Hyptis suaveolens (L.) Poit., commonly known as bushmint, is a perennial shrub found in tropical and subtropical regions. Its essential oil, extracted from the leaves, is recognized for antimicrobial, antifungal, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties. This review offers an in-depth analysis of the oil's chemical composition and biological activities, highlighting the influence of geographical and extraction factors on its complex mix of monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, and volatile compounds. While the plant holds significant medicinal potential, its invasive nature requires sustainable utilization strategies. Further research is essential to fully harness its therapeutic benefits.

Keywords

Hyptis Suaveolens, Essential Oil, Chemical Composition, Biological Properties.

Introduction

The Lamiaceae family (previously known as Labiatae), commonly known as the mint or sage family, includes a diverse range of aromatic plants widely recognized for their medicinal properties [1]. This botanical family comprises numerous genera and species of culinary herbs that are used in traditional medicine systems worldwide due to their therapeutic benefits and distinctive aromatic profiles. Plants in the Lamiaceae family are often characterized by their square stems, opposite leaves, and glandular hairs that produce essential oils contributing to their unique fragrances and biological activities [2]. Medicinal plants from the Lamiaceae family, such as *Basil* (Tulsi), *Mentha* (mint), *Salvia* (sage), and *Thymus* (thyme), are renowned for their wide array of applications in treating various health conditions. For instance, *Mentha* species are frequently used for digestive issues and respiratory ailments due to their carminative and antispasmodic properties [3].

Objective of study

The present review thus aims to analyze the available data from recent previous studies of the biological activity of *H. suaveolens* essential oil.

Review of Literature

Salvia officinalis (sage) has been traditionally employed for its anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects, while *Thymus vulgaris* (thyme) is valued for its antiseptic and expectorant properties [4,5]. The use of *Ocimum* species (Tulsi) has been extensively documented in Ayurveda and its biological properties continue to be an active area of research. These plants are rich in essential oils that contain monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, and other bioactive compounds, which contribute to their therapeutic and aromatic characteristics. Genus *Hyptis* has about 400 species [6], among which, *Hyptis suaveolens* (L.) Poit. (*Mesopharum suaveolens*) commonly known as bushmint, 'Vilayati Tulsi' (Hindi) and bhustrena (Sanskrit) stands out for its potent aromatic properties and medicinal uses. Originally a native of Central America, it is now found in all tropical and subtropical climate zones around the world. It has high adaptability and has documented locations in almost every state in India. Although it may grow in semi-arid conditions, it does best in warm tropical locations with high rainfall. [7] It is an invasive weed which is significant for its essential oil abundant in monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes, responsible for its antimicrobial, antifungal, and insecticidal activities [8]. This plant's essential oil exhibits significant variability in its chemical composition depending on the geographic location and environmental conditions, leading to diverse chemotypes. Apart

from its antioxidant properties, it also has diuretic, antidiabetic, anti-fungal and anti-inflammatory [9,10,11,12] that account for its usage as a traditional medicine in various cultures worldwide. Biological properties of its extracts and essential oils such as antibacterial [13], antinociceptive [14], and adulticidal properties have been investigated [15]. Though its nutritional value [16], medicinal properties and traditional uses [17] have been reviewed, comprehensive review on phytochemical, and biological aspects of essential oils of *H. suaveolens* is lacking.

Plant description

It starts its vegetative phase from either a perennating rootstock or viable seeds from the previous cycle when the monsoon rains begin [18]. The shrub, reaching up to 1.5 meters in height, has a stem that is obtusely four-angled and thinly hairy. The leaves are ovate, acute, and hispid on the underside, while the upper surface is nearly hairless. They have petioles that can grow up to 5 cm long. The flowers are arranged in clusters of 1 to 12, with a calyx tube that is 8 mm long, tubular, and 10-ribbed, featuring glandular hairs and spinulose teeth that are 4 mm long. The corolla is 5 mm long, with short, glabrous lobes that are blue. The nutlets measure 4 x 2.5 mm, are compressed with a ridge on the dorsal surface, pubescent, deep brown, and become mucilaginous when wet [19]. Although 25 to 30 °C is ideal for seed germination, seeds can germinate in a wide range of temperatures, from roughly 10 to 40 °C [20].

Figure 1- (a):*H. suaveolens* plant at Maldevta, Dehradun, Uttarakhand; (b) Flowering and fruiting body; (c) fresh and dry seeds

Methodology

This evaluation relies on an examination of research papers that were obtained from offline sources such as books like Wealth of India and digital sources such as SciFinder, ScienceDirect, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Wiley Online. Search on digital platforms was carried out first by using major keywords 'Hyptis suaveolens' and then combining the words 'Essential Oil', 'Chemical constituents', 'Chemistry', 'Phytochemistry', 'Traditional uses', and 'Biological Activity' with major keywords up to year 2024. The earliest research paper was found dating back to 1970.

Analysis

Traditional uses

Hyptis suaveolens is widely recognized for its traditional medicinal uses across more than 23 countries. Its use has been documented in The Ayurveda, Chinese Traditional Medicine and African traditional medicinal system. Various parts of the plant are utilized in traditional medicine, reflecting its broad therapeutic potential. These applications include both in vivo and in vitro usage of the plant through various methods. In Bangladesh, the seeds of Hyptis suaveolens are used to treat ailments like gastrointestinal disorders [21,22] by soaking them in water and ingesting. Stems are juiced to treat stomach ache in children [23]. While in Brazil, a tea is brewed with aerial parts of the plant to relieve diarrhoea and stomach inflammation [24,25].

Use of aerial parts to make a decoction for treating skin conditions has been recorded in China [26]. The roots are stewed with chicken to make a dish that helps cure infertility upon consumption [27].

In India, a *Beedi* made of *H. suaveolens* leaves is used to aid with respiratory problems [28] and its leaves are used to treat surface wounds on skin. In Nigeria, the entire plant has been documented for its use in repelling mosquitoes [29,30]. Several scientific studies conducted in Africa have evaluated the efficacy of *H. suaveolens* as a mosquito repellent, producing promising results. [31,32]. In the Phillipines, skin irritation and joint pain are treated by soaking in bath water prepared with leaves of *H. suaveolens* [33]. A concoction prepared from its roots is also served as an appetizer [34]. In Senegal, a tea made from seeping its stem, flowers and seeds is used to treat cough and cold [35].

Chemical constituents of *H. suaveolens* essential oil

Research on the essential oil from this plant began in the early 20th century. The essential oil derived from aerial parts of the plant, is typically pale yellow to light green, has been described as having a "herbaceous" aroma with citrus and slightly minty

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undertones. The yield of essential varies significantly, ranging from 0.2% to 0.4% [36,37.38].

Table 1: Chemical constituents identified in the essential oil of *H. suaveolens* (L.) Poit.

No.	Compounds	Concentration Range	Plant part	References
Monoterpene Hydrocarbons				
1.	α -thujene	0.2 - 1.09	L, F, Fr	[46] [49] [52] [55]
2.	β -thujene	8.07	L	[47]
3.	α -pinene	0.7 - 10.09	L, F Fr, St	[46] [47] [48] [49] [50] [52] [55]
4.	sabinene	0.7 - 29.42	L, F, Fr	[46] [50] [53] [55]
5.	β -pinene	2.11 - 11.7	L, F, St	[46] [48] [49] [52] [55]
6.	α -myrcene	0.26 - 8.7	L, F, Fr	[46] [52] [55]
7.	β -myrcene	5.3	L	[49]
8.	b-carene	1.1	L	[49]
9.	δ -2-carene	0.49	L	[46]
10.	α -phellandrene	0.7 - 22.78	L, Fr, St	[46] [47] [48] [55]
11.	α -terpinene	0.29 - 1.05	L	[46] [47]
12.	p-cymene	0.76 - 6.1	L, St	[46] [47] [55]
13.	limonene	0.7 - 8.48	L, F	[46] [47] [52]
14.	(Z)- β -ocimene	0.07 - 11.7	L, St	[46] [55] [57]
15.	(E)- β -ocimene	0.12	L	[46]
16.	γ -terpinene	0.2 - 6.3	L, F, Fr, St	[46] [47] [52] [55]
17.	thymol	1.27	L	[54]
18.	sylvestrene	3.4	St	[55]
19.	merteryl acetate	1.1	St	[55]
20.	camphor	0.8 - 1.1	L, Fr	[49] [54] [55]
21.	camphene	0.39 - 5.7	L, F	[47] [49] [52] [57]
22.	bicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-one, 1,3,3-trimethyl	2.08	L	[48]
23.	terpinolene	0.3 - 6.6	L, F, Fr, St	[47] [52] [53] [55]
24.	o-cymene	0.7 - 4.2	L, F	[47] [52]
25.	allo-ocimene	8.67	L	[47]
26.	fenchone	2.7 - 17.2	L, Fr	[53] [55] [57]
27.	α -fenchol	0.59 - 11.8	L	[47] [53] [54] [57]
28.	fenchyl acetate	0.1	L, F	[52]
29.	3-cyclohexen-1-ol,4-methyl-1-(1-methylethyl)	3.55	L	[48]
30.	(E)-4,8-dimethylnona-1,3,7-triene	0.3	L, F	[52]
Oxygenated monoterpenes				
31.	cis-sabinene hydrate	0.61 - 2.02	L	[46] [47] [57]
32.	1,8-cineole / eucalyptol	1.72 - 44.4	L, Fr	[46] [47] [48] [49] [50] [53] [55]
33.	trans-sabinene hydrate	0.4	L	[57]
34.	linalool	0.43 - 1.7	L, St	[46] [47] [49] [55]
35.	linalool trans-oxide	6.5	L	[53]
36.	cis-p-menth-2-en-1-ol	0.26 - 0.28	L	[46] [47]
37.	t-sabinol	0.15	L	[46]
38.	(-)-4-terpineol	1.96	L	[47]
39.	p-cymen-8-ol	0.23	L	[46]
40.	α -terpineol	0.4 - 1.4	L, Fr, Sr	[46] [55]
41.	terpinen-4-ol	0.4 - 6.8	L, Fr, St	[46] [49] [54] [55]
42.	borneol	1.2	L, Fr	[55] [57]
43.	cis- β -terpineol	0.21	L	[47]
44.	bornyl acetate	0.2 - 0.6	L, F, St	[52] [55]
45.	(E)-ocimene oxide	1.37	L	[47]
46.	α -bergamotene	1.7 - 2.67	L	[47] [49]
Sesquiterpene hydrocarbons				
47.	α -cubebene	0.3	L	[49]
48.	β -cubebene	0.3	Fr	[55]
49.	δ -elemene	0.2 - 1.17	L, F	[46] [52]
50.	α -copaene	0.09 - 1.32	L, F	[46] [48] [49] [50] [52]
51.	β -elemene	0.47 - 0.78	L, F	[46] [47] [52]
52.	rimuene	5.73	L	[50]
53.	β -cedrene	0.14	L	[46]
54.	β -caryophyllene	9.47 - 40.2	L, F	[46] [47] [51] [52] [53]
55.	β -bourbonene	0.1	L	[57]
56.	β -gurjunene	0.23 - 1.6	L	[46] [49]
57.	γ -elemene	1.2 - 2.57	L	[46] [48] [49] [51]
58.	aromadendrene	0.2 - 0.32	L, F	[46] [52]
59.	α -humelene	0.5 - 6.7	L, F	[46] [47] [49] [50] [52]
60.	ar-curcumene	0.1	L	[52]
61.	alloaromadendrene	0.40 - 1.8	L	[46] [54]
62.	γ -muurolene	0.28	L	[46]
63.	germacrene D	0.17 - 5.21	L, F	[46] [47] [48] [52]
64.	α -selinene	2.32	L	[50]
65.	β -selinene	0.89 - 0.9	L	[46] [49]
66.	longifolene	0.4	L	[49]
67.	bicyclogermacrene	0.7 - 9.7	L, F	[46] [52] [53]
68.	dehydro-isolongifolene	2.3 - 8.4	L	[53]
69.	β -bisabolene	0.5 - 2.8	L, F	[52]

70.	β -sesquiphellandrene	0.1	F	[52]
71.	γ -cadinene	0.36	L	[46]
72.	δ -cadinene	0.09 - 0.52	L, F	[46] [50] [52] [57]
73.	germacrene b	0.27 - 0.52	L	[46] [50]
74.	trans α -caryophyllene	13.66	L	[50]
75.	ar-turmenone	3.4	L, F	[52]
76.	curlone	0.4 - 1.2	L, F	[52]
77.	6,10,14-trimethylpentadecan-2-one	0.4 - 0.8	L, F	[52]
78.	Z-trans- α bergamotol	1.3 - 3.11	L	[47] [48]
79.	trans- α -bergamotene	4.2	L	[51]
80.	α -farnesene	2.8	L	[49]
81.	(E)- β -farnesene	0.46 - 0.5	L, F	[47] [52]
82.	(Z)- β -farnesene	0.1	F	[52]
83.	cyclohexane,1-ethenyl-1-methyl-2,4-bis(1-methylethenyl)	2.79	L	[48]
84.	bicyclo[7.2.0]undec-4-ene,4,11,11-trimethyl-8-methylene	17.3	L	[48]
85.	phenanthrene,7-ethenyl-1,2,3,4,4a,4b,5,6,7,8,8a,9-dodecahydro-1,1,4b-tetramethyl/ rimuene	2.68	L	[48]
Oxygenated sesquiterpenes				
86.	caryophyllene oxide	2.08-17.6	L, F	[46] [47] [50] [51] [52] [54]
87.	(e)-nerolidol	0.7	L, F	[52]
88.	spathulenol	0.4 –11.09	L, F	[46] [50] [52] [54]
89.	trans-calamenene	0.3	L	[57]
90.	elemol	0.6	L	[56]
91.	rosifoliol	0.1	L	[57]
92.	guaiol	3.8	L	[52]
93.	14-hydroxy-9-epi-(E)-caryophyllene	0.5	L	[52]
94.	humulene oxide i	0.3	L	[52]
95.	humulene oxide ii	0.4-2.1	L, F	[52]
96.	globulol	0.62	L	[46]
97.	cubenol	1.07	L	[46]
98.	1-epi-cubenol	0.4-1.7	L, F	[52]
99.	caryophylla-3(15),7(14)-dien-6-ol	0.2-0.8	L, F	[52]
100.	β -eudesmol	0.13	L	[46]
101.	τ -cadinol	0.4	L	[57]
102.	α -oxobisabolene	0.1	L, F	[52]
103.	α -cadinol	0.45- 0.8	L, F	[46] [52] [57]
Diterpenes				
104.	isopimara-8,15-diene	0.4	F	[52]
105.	mancool	1.0	F	[52]
106.	abietatriene	0.8-1.0	F, L	[52] [57]
107.	abietadiene	0.7-4.7	F, L	[52] [57]
108.	abieta-8(14),13(15)-diene	0.2	F	[52]
109.	phytol	2.7-9.9	L, F	[52]
110.	retinol	1.6	L	[51]
111.	7-isopropyl-1,1,4a-trimethyl-1,2,3,4,4a,9,10,10a-octahydrophenanthrene	1.02	L	[48]
Alcohols				
112.	(z)-3-hexenol	0.15	L	[47]
113.	octen-3-ol	5.36	L	[48]
114.	dihydrotachysterol	17.2	L	[51]
Aldehydes				
115.	nonanal	1.4	L	[54]
Ketones				
116.	cryptone	tr	L	[57]
Hydrocarbons				
117.	1H-3a,7-methanoazulene, octahydro-1,4,9,9-tetramethyl	1.13	L	[48]
118.	p-xylene	3.7	L	[54]
119.	o-xylene	3.6	L	[54]
120.	heneicosane	0.2	F	[52]
121.	bicyclo[3.1.1]hept-2-ene	1.47	L	[48]
122.	bicyclo[3.1.0]hexane	6.82	L	[48]
123.	1,3,6,10-cyclotetradecaetraene, 3,7,11-trimethyl-14-(1-methylethyl)	0.58	L	[48]
124.	cyclohexene,4-methyl-3-(1-methylethylidene)	4.52	L	[48]
125.	bicyclo[3.1.1]hept-2-ene-216-dimethyl-6-(4-methyl-3-pentenyl)	2.7	L	[51]
126.	naphthalene,2,3,4,4a,5,6-hexahydro-1,4a-dimethyl-7-(1-methylethyl)	1.8	L	[51]
127.	7-isopropyl-1,1,4a-trimethyl-1,2,3,4,4a,9,10,10-octahydrophenanthrene	8.3	L	[51]
128.	bicyclo[4.1.0]-3-heptene,2-isopropenyl-5-isopropyl-7,7-dimethyl	2.7	L	[51]
Phenylpropanoids				
129.	estragole	16.3	St	[55]
130.	1-phenyl-hepta-1,3,5-triene	0.6	L	[52]

L: leaves, F: flowers, Fr: fruit, St: stem

A total of 130 compounds can be categorized as monoterpene hydrocarbons, oxygenated monoterpenes, sesquiterpene hydrocarbons, oxygenated sesquiterpenes, diterpenes, phenylpropanoids, alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, and hydrocarbons have been identified through phytochemical screening of the essential oil *H. suaveolens* from all over the world (Table 1). Thirty of the 130 were hydrocarbons classified as monoterpenes, fifteen as oxygenated monoterpenes, thirty as sesquiterpenes, seventeen as oxygenated sesquiterpenes, seven as diterpenes, three as alcohols, one as an aldehyde, one as ketone, eleven hydrocarbons, and two phenylpropanoids. Terpenes are the most abundant and structurally varied naturally occurring plant compounds, according to Zwenger [39]. Monoterpenes are the C₁₀ representatives of the terpenoid family and are formally considered to be constructed of two isoprene units [40]. One DMAPP (Dimethylallyl pyrophosphate) and one IPP (Isopentenyl pyrophosphate) molecule, which are often connected head-to-tail to produce all-trans geranyl diphosphate (GPP), are the building blocks of monoterpenes. GPP may be folded into tricyclic, bicyclic, and monocyclic structures, and then changed to yield more than a thousand different monoterpenes. Monoterpenes are lipophilic volatile compounds that are present in floral odors, essential oils, and protective resins of conifers. They are responsible for the unique flavor and aroma of many plants [41]. Sesquiterpenoids are a class of natural products that are derived from farnesyl pyrophosphate (FPP) and are made up of three isoprene units [42].

A plant's biogenic volatile organic compound (BVOC) response is mostly mediated by sesquiterpenes. They have a key role in the defense mechanisms of plants against pests and predators [43]. Diterpenes are produced via the synthesis and chemical modification of carbon skeletons from geranylgeranyl diphosphate, a common isoprene precursor. Various diterpenes have been identified from a wide range of species of flora and fauna. In addition to medicines and physiologically active compounds like phytohormones, these diterpenes also include antibiotics [44]. In certain plants, phenylalanine and tyrosine are the precursors in the shikimic acid pathway, which produces phenylpropanoids or cinnamic acids. [45].

Several common main compounds were identified. Prominent monoterpene hydrocarbons have been identified as sabinene (0.7 - 29.42%), β -pinene (2.11 - 11.7%), β -myrcene (5.3%), α -phellandrene (0.7 - 22.78%), p-cymene (0.76 - 6.1%), limonene (0.7 - 8.48%), (Z)- β -ocimene (0.07 - 11.7%), fenchone (2.7 - 17.2%), and α -fenchol (0.59 - 11.8%). 1,8-cineole / eucalyptol (1.72 - 44.4%) was the dominant oxygenated monoterpene. The main sesquiterpene hydrocarbons were found to be β -caryophyllene (9.47 - 40.2%), α -humelene (0.5 - 6.7%), germacrene D (0.17 - 5.21%), and bicyclogermacrene (0.7 - 9.7%). The two predominant oxygenated sesquiterpenes were spathulenol (0.4 - 11.09%) and caryophyllene oxide (2.08 - 17.6%). The major diterpene (0.7 - 4.7%) was abietadiene. α -copaene, β -elemene, γ -elemene, δ -cadinene, α -cadinol, camphor, linalool, bornyl acetate, and α -thujene were observed as the common minor compounds.

Pharmacology

The chemical composition of the oil varies significantly across different geographic regions, influenced by factors such as climate, soil type, and plant genetics. This variation has led to the identification of distinct chemotypes, each with unique pharmacological profiles. The essential oil has demonstrated notable antimicrobial, antifungal, and insecticidal properties, making it a valuable resource in traditional medicine and potential modern therapeutic applications.

A detailed summary of the chemical composition and corresponding pharmacological activities reported in various studies is provided in Table 2, offering a comprehensive overview of the current knowledge on this versatile plant. The DPPH test [7,10], FRAP assay [64], and orthophenanthroline assay [72] have all been used to examine the essential oil of *H. suaveolens* for its antioxidant activity. Significant anti-cancer properties of *H. suaveolens* essential oil have been assessed using the MTT test on the human breast cancer cell line MCF-7 [75]. According to studies, *Hyptis suaveolens* contains phytochemicals that are effective against a variety of fungus, like *Trichophyton rubrum* [64], *Rhizopus stolonifera*, *Aspergillus species* [61], *Candida albicans*, and *Fusarium oxysporum f.sp. gladioli* [67]. Due to its potent antibacterial activity against bacterial strains like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [59], *Shigella dysenteria* [69], *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *Bacillus cereus* [71], the essential oil of *H. suaveolens* can potentially find use as a bio-preservative [64]. Evaluations of *H. suaveolens* essential oil's insecticidal qualities have been carried out on *Anopheles gambiae* [68], *Tenebroides mauritanicus* [69], and *Rhipicephalus microplus* [76]. Furthermore, it has proven to be highly effective in killing *Aedes aegypti* [66] and *Culex quinquefasciatus* [65] larvae. In addition, it has a strong repellent effect on female *Culex* and *Anopheles* mosquitoes [71]. These results support the traditional African medicine's usage of this herb as a repellent. In vivo tests have revealed that it also demonstrates acute phytotoxicity against *E. crus-galli* [74] and cytotoxicity against mice [71], *D. melanogaster*, *A. salina* [73], and *Allium cepa* [74].

Table 2: Pharmacological Activities of *Hyptis suaveolens* Essential Oil from recent studies.

Location	Biological activity test	Key findings	Ref
Adamawa, Nigeria	Antimicrobial Activity (Microbroth dilution technique)	HSEO showed anti-mycobacterium activity when tested on strain 7H9/ADC with MIC of 3.13 %. This activity was compared with standard drug Rifampicin which also has MIC of 0.1 µg/ml.	[58]
Kerala, India	Antimicrobial Activity Disc diffusion, MIC assays	The essential oil was highly effective against <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (MIC 1.56 µL/mL). It showed good activity against <i>Escherichia coli</i> (MIC 6.25 µL/mL). <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> had a moderate sensitivity (MIC 16.67 µL/mL). <i>Proteus vulgaris</i> showed the least sensitivity (MIC 50 µL/mL). <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> had a MIC of 25 µL/mL. The oil's activity compares favorably with antibiotics Gentamycin and Chloramphenicol, especially against <i>S. aureus</i>	[59]
Lagos, Nigeria	Antimicrobial Activity (MIC and MBC assays) Antifungal Activity (MFC assay)	Antibacterial: Effective against <i>E. coli</i> ATCC25922 (MIC = 23.3 µL/mL; MBC = 36.7 µL/mL) and <i>S. aureus</i> ATCC25923 (MIC = 26.7 µL/mL; MBC = 46.7 µL/mL). Bacteriostatic effect observed with dose-dependent loss of outer membrane proteins in <i>E. coli</i> ATCC25922. Antifungal: Highest sensitivity with <i>Candida albicans</i> (MFC = 53.3 µL/mL); moderate to low sensitivity with <i>Aspergillus niger</i> and <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> . New chemotype discovered in Lagos with distinct compound profile.	[60]
Lucknow, India	Antifungal (Poisoned food technique (PF) and volatile activity assay (VA) on <i>Fusarium oxysporum f.sp. gladioli</i>)	Complete inhibition of mycelial growth at 0.998 µg/mL (PF) and 0.748 µg/mL (VA). Fungicidal at 1.247 µg/mL (PF) and 0.998 µg/mL (VA). 100% inhibition of conidial germination at 0.450 µg/mL.	[61]
Bananeiras, Brazil	Antifungal Activity (In vitro MIC and MFC assays)	HSEO inhibited growth of <i>Aspergillus</i> species, with MIC and MFC of 40 and 80 µL/mL, respectively; oil caused significant morphological changes in fungi	[62]
Pù Hoạt Nature Reserve, Vietnam	Antimicrobial Activity	Enterococcus faecalis ATCC 29921 Leaf Oil: MIC = 16.0 µg/mL, IC ₅₀ = 5.78 µg/mL Flower Oil: MIC = 64.0 µg/mL, IC ₅₀ = 20.45 µg/mL Bacillus cereus ATCC 14579 Leaf Oil: MIC = 32.0 µg/mL, IC ₅₀ = 9.35 µg/mL Flower Oil: MIC = 64.0 µg/mL, IC ₅₀ = 26.78 µg/mL Candida albicans ATCC 10231 Leaf Oil: MIC = 16.0 µg/mL, IC ₅₀ = 6.78 µg/mL Flower Oil: MIC = 16.0 µg/mL, IC ₅₀ = 6.78 µg/mL Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 25923 MIC = 256.0 µg/mL for both leaf and flower oils	[63]
Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso	Antioxidant Activity (DPPH assay, FRAP assay) Antimicrobial Activity (Well diffusion method, MIC, MBC, MFC) Biopreservation (Conservation test of ground beef)	DPPH Assay: IC ₅₀ = 16.367 ± 0.074 µL (better than ascorbic acid, but lower than BHT and quercetin). FRAP Assay: Lower reducing power compared to ascorbic acid Well Diffusion Method: Largest inhibition diameter with <i>Shigella dysenteriae</i> (43.667 mm), smallest with <i>Candida albicans</i> (10.667 mm). MIC: Ranged from 0.203% to 2.083%. MBC: Ranged from 0.625% to 5%. MFC: Active against <i>A. niger</i> , fungistatic on <i>C. albicans</i> . Initial Microbial Load: 7.0×10 ⁴ CFU/g (total aerobic mesophilic bacteria), 1.0×10 ⁴ CFU/g (total coliforms), 5.0×10 ² CFU/g (thermotolerant coliforms). With Essential Oil: On Day 1, microbial load was 3×10 ⁴ CFU/g; on Day 7, it was 7.3×10 ⁴ CFU/g. Significant reduction (42%) in microbial load compared to untreated meat. Total Coliforms: Initial count of 1.5×10 ⁴ CFU/g; Day 7 count 8.0×10 ³ CFU/g with essential oil, showing an 80% reduction. Thermotolerant Coliforms: Day 1 count of 6.0×10 ² CFU/g; Day 7 count of 1.0×10 ² CFU/g with essential oil, showing an 84% reduction.	[64]
Amapá, Brazil	Larvicidal Activity (Against <i>Culex quinquefasciatus</i> larvae)	Nanoemulsion of <i>H. suaveolens</i> essential oil showed high larvicidal activity. CL₅₀ values: 102.41 ppm (24h), 70.81 ppm (48h). Mortality in surfactant control < 9%. Micrograph images showed integument changes in larvae.	[65]
Tamil Nadu, India	Larvicidal Activity (Against <i>Aedes aegypti</i> larvae)	High mortality rate observed at ≥200 ppm after 12 and 24 hours; LC₅₀ : 32.85 ppm, LC₉₀ : 66.54 ppm. Histological analysis showed severe damage in midgut and cortex, attributed to volatile components like caryophyllene and caryophyllene oxide.	[66]
Kerala, India	Antioxidant Activity (DPPH Assay) Larvicidal Activity (Lethal Concentration against <i>A. stephensi</i> larvae)	EC₅₀ values: 22.76 µg/mL (leaf oil), 26.18 µg/mL (inflorescence oil), compared to 17.57 µg/mL for ascorbic acid. LC₅₀ values: 39.08 µg/mL (inflorescence oil), 33.19 µg/mL (leaf oil).	[67]

Dang, Cameroon	Insecticidal Activity (CDC bottle bioassay)	HSEO caused 100% mortality of <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> adults at 200 mg/bottle; LC50 = 5.27 mg/bottle, showing high toxicity compared to other oils	[68]
Abomey-calavi, Benin	Insecticidal activity (Contact Toxicity Test and Repellency Test)	Insecticidal: 100% mortality of <i>Tenebrioidea mauritanicus</i> at 0.5 µL/g of peanut after 24 hours Repellent: 100% repellency at 0.06 µL/cm ² , high repellency class (V)	[69]
Adamawa, Cameroon	Adulticidal Activity of essential oil (Mortality of <i>Anopheles gambiae</i>) Repellent Activity of Cream Formulation (Protection from <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> bites)	93.33% mortality at 100 mg/bottle. LC50: 3.22 mg/bottle for <i>H. suaveolens</i> oil and 6.15 mg/bottle for <i>L. adoensis</i> oil. 100% protection for up to 120 minutes with cream at 8.0 mg/cm ² . No bites for at least 150 minutes with essential oil cream at 4.0 mg/cm ² .	[70]
Ilorin, Nigeria	Mosquito Repellent Activity (Repellency against female <i>Anopheles</i> and <i>Culex</i> mosquitoes) Toxicity in Mice Effects on (haematological, liver, and kidney functions)	100% efficacy for up to 60 minutes with EO in water (1:99). Increased WBC, RBC, HCT, HGB levels; reduced serum albumin, total and direct bilirubin, and total protein; increased serum urea and creatinine levels. No significant effect on ALP, ALT, and AST activities.	[71]
Ceará, Brazil	Antioxidant Activity Orthophenanthroline assay (Fe ²⁺ chelation and Fe ³⁺ reduction)	Fe²⁺ Chelation: Moderate activity at highest concentration (480 µg/mL); suggests ability to chelate Fe ²⁺ and oxidize Fe ²⁺ to Fe ³⁺ . Fe³⁺ Reduction: Significant increase in absorbance in a dose-dependent manner; highest concentration showed moderate reduction followed by an increase in absorbance.	[72]
Ceará, Brazil	Toxicity (Acute Toxicity and Locomotor Activity)	Essential oil showed significant toxicity with LC50 of 15.5 µg/mL in <i>D. melanogaster</i> and 49.72 µg/mL in <i>A. salina</i> and caused impairment of locomotor behavior in flies.	[73]
Chandigarh, India	Phytotoxicity (Bioassay on <i>Oryza sativa</i> and <i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>) Cytotoxicity (Cell division assay in <i>Allium cepa</i>)	Phytotoxicity: EO inhibited germination and seedling growth of <i>E. crus-galli</i> completely at ≥ 2 mg/mL, with much less effect on rice (~40% inhibition). EO also caused visible injury and reduction in chlorophyll content in <i>E. crus-galli</i> . Cytotoxicity: EO caused a ~63% decrease in mitotic index and induced chromosomal aberrations and cytological changes.	[74]
Pollachi, Tamil Nadu	Anticancer Activity (MTT assay on MCF-7 human breast cancer cell line)	Essential oil showed concentration-dependent activity with an IC50 value of 90.6 µg/mL.	[75]
Benin	Antiparasitic (Toxicity to <i>R. (B.) microplus</i> females: Multi-dose immersion test on reproductive parameters like egg laying inhibition and oviposition delay)	Egg laying inhibition: - 65% at 1% β-caryophyllene - 98% at 2% β-caryophyllene - 69% at 3% eucalyptol-rich oil Oviposition delay: - 168 hours at 1% β-caryophyllene - 144 hours at 2% β-caryophyllene - 72 hours at 3% eucalyptol-rich oil	[76]

Ref: references

Conclusion

Aromatic plants have long been integral to traditional medicine, valued for their inherent biological properties in addressing everyday ailments. Due to the growing trend of organic and mindful consumption, the market for these plants and their derivatives continues to rise in the food, pharmaceutical, and other industries. This review provides a comprehensive overview of the ethnomedical significance, chemical composition, and biological activities of the essential oil of *Hyptis suaveolens*. The plant's significance is evidenced by its diverse traditional uses across the globe. A total of 130 compounds have been identified in the essential oil, with many in vitro and in vivo studies supporting its traditional applications, including antibacterial, insect repellent, and insecticidal effects. While extensive research has been conducted on the plant's extracts, the corresponding data for its essential oil is largely unavailable. In order to harness this important aromatic plant for its medicinal potential, more research is needed in the areas of pharmacology, mechanism, and bioassay-guided isolation of biologically active components. This research will help to understand the scientific relationship between chemical composition and biological effects, as well as the basis of traditional uses. By highlighting this disparity, this review aims to identify key research gaps and guide future investigations in this area. Despite such extensive research and documented traditional uses, this plant remains neglected and underutilized. As a result, this plant requires a lot of attention before it is fully appreciated and utilized. The current review serves as an overview of knowledge from recent investigations that could provide researchers working on future studies of this valuable aromatic plant of medicinal importance a clean perspective.

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